

The Spread of Toxoplasmosis in Women within Al-Rifai District

Rehab Issa Hashem Suhail ✉

Department of Pathological Analysis, College of Science, University of Sumer, Iraq

Shimaa Ahmed Mutab Nayef

Pathological Analysis Department, College of Applied Science, University of Fallujah, Iraq

Teeba Sabah Daham Mohammed

Department of Pathological Analysis, College of Applied Sciences, University of Fallujah, Iraq

Yaqeen Mohammed Mahmud

Department of Pathological Analysis, College of Applied Sciences, Alfallujah University, Iraq

Abdalmrhman Falah Omar Ali

Pathological Analysis Department, College of Applied Science, University of Fallujah, Iraq

More Information

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Abstract

Toxoplasmosis is a disease caused by a single-celled protozoan parasite called *Toxoplasma gondii*. Infection occurs when a person inadvertently swallows toxoplasma cysts found in cat feces or contaminated meat. The infection usually does not cause symptoms, but some people have swollen lymph nodes, fever, and vague malaise, and sometimes a sore throat or blurred vision and eye pain. In people with a weakened immune system due to AIDS or another condition, *toxoplasmosis* can reactivate, usually infecting the brain. A reactivated infection can lead to weakness, confusion, convulsions, coma, or spread throughout the body. There are two hosts: the final host, which is cats, plays an important role, and sheep, goats, and humans may also play the intermediate host.

The infection is more severe if the fetus becomes infected early in pregnancy. The result may be a slowly growing fetus, an early miscarriage, stillbirth, or a baby being born with birth defects (called congenital anomalies). Congenital toxoplasmosis can cause problems with vision disturbances, intellectual disability, and other abnormalities.

The current study was conducted to demonstrate the prevalence of toxoplasmosis in women in the city of Al-Rifai. Statistical data was collected from the virology laboratory at Al-Rifai Hospital for 100 female samples infected with the disease and diagnosed in the laboratory at different ages from 19-43. After that, a statistical analysis of the samples according to age groups was conducted and a difference was identified in them. Infection rates: The highest percentage of infections was 10% in the age group 29-33, and the lowest percentage was 1% in the age group 39-43, and the number of positive results was 22%.

Introduction

Toxoplasmosis is a parasitic infection caused by the intracellular protozoan *Toxoplasma gondii*, its belongs to the Phylum Apicomplexa that contains intracellular

parasites so as to have a naturally polarized cell structure and an intricate cytoskeletal and organelles arrangement at their apical end [1]. Infections caused by *Toxoplasma gondii* and Cytomegalovirus (CMV)

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reflect the common reasons of congenital infections and bad obstetrics consequences worldwide [2,3]. These pathogens in the TORCH group constitute 2-3% of congenital anomalies [4].

Have long been known to be linked to defective and unsuccessful pregnancies. However, it is one of the major causes of perinatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developed and underdeveloped nations [5]. During the pregnancy's earliest trimesters, the primary infections of Toxoplasmosis may cause a wide variety of clinical symptoms [6]. Additionally, infections during the first trimester of pregnancy may result in fetal mortality, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and malformations [7].

In the primary trimester of pregnancy, the chance of Toxoplasmosis transitioning to the fetus is less than 6%; by the third trimester, it is between 60 and 80% percent. Although it is uncommon, the entry into the fetus during embryogenesis can cause severe congenital malformations [8]. Broad ranges of clinical symptoms, such as intracranial calcifications, jaundice, lymphadenopathy, hepatosplenomegaly, and skin rash, could be caused by these pathogenic infections, during the later stages of pregnancy as opposed to the earlier stages, when the infections are either latent (asymptomatic) or may cause signs [9]. Infection severity differs depending on the baby's gestational age, the organisms' virulence, the extent of placental damage, and the mother's health [10].

The ability of *T. gondii* to persist in the central nervous system of a variety of hosts makes it one of the most successful parasites in the world, Intracellular parasitism is a tactic used by several eukaryotic microorganisms that have the capacity to enter and multiply inside cells of vertebrate hosts (Weiss and Dubey, 2009). Some can only enter a limited range of cell types, as is the case with *Plasmodium* and *Leishmania*, which attack reticulocytes (erythrocytes) and macrophages, respectively. *Trypanosoma cruzi* and other parasites can enter nearly all kinds of cells [11,12].

Toxoplasmosis is a disease that has an economic impact on animal production and has raised public health concerns since it can cause miscarriages and complications for newborns in humans, the intermediate hosts for *T. gondii* are mammals and birds, and the cat is the definitive host. The infection is mostly contracted by drinking water or eating food that has *T. gondii* tissue cysts or oocysts in it [13]. Toxoplasmosis in Humans is closely linked with eating of raw or undercooked food, meat taken from domestic animals infected with *T. gondii* is considered the main and important source of infection in humans [14].

The disease toxoplasmosis, when affecting immunocompetent people causes general symptoms to appear (nonspecific symptoms) such as fever, muscle

pain, headache and swollen lymph nodes [15]. It causes major health problems for people, especially in cases suffer from a weakened immune system and in children born to infected mothers [16]. whereas in immunosuppressed people, it can be fatal [17].

Toxoplasma gondii all warm-blooded mammalians' nucleated cells are susceptible to infection, and it can survive in all nucleated cells, including blood cells in the acute stage, by producing a specific vacuole that protect the parasite from the host cell's immune response. The parasite may develop a cyst in the tissues of the central nervous system, eyes, and skeletal muscles during the chronic stage, which can last the whole lifetime of the host, the cysts can rupture and release highly invasive trophozoite, which, if the host has a compromised immune system, can lead to recurrent infections and even death [18].

Primary infection with Toxoplasmosis during pregnancy period can lead to bad outcomes, which are begin unclearly or asymptomatic and so difficult to identify on a clinical basis [19]. Transmission of *T. gondii* to the fetus was linked to primary maternal infection during pregnancy [20].

The most severe clinical manifestation of *T. gondii* infection was congenital Toxoplasmosis., which often does not significantly harm the pregnant mother, but the fetus is affected by it., in the short or long term, resulting stillbirth, spontaneous abortion, cerebral calcifications, hydrocephalus, macro or microcephalus, retinochoroiditis, and ocular or central nervous system alterations [21].

The transmission rate of maternal infection to the fetus was estimated to be about 45%; of these, 60% are sub-clinical infections, 9% resulting in death of the fetus and 30% have severe damages such as hydrocephalus, intracerebral calcification, chorioretinitis and mental retardation [22]. The majority of perinatal infections, toxoplasmosis, was linked to an unfavourable pregnancy outcome and accounts for 2 to 3 percent of all congenital abnormalities (30). One of the most common causes of abortion and congenital abnormalities in infected women was the infectious illness toxoplasmosis, It is to result in reproductive miscarriage [23].

Additionally, there are new, accurate, sensitive, and specific methods to diagnose *T. gondii* infection using serological teste, which might be very helpful to distinguish between chronic and acute sickness [24].

Aims of the study

Detect speared of Toxoplasmosis in women in AL-Rifai district.

Classification of *T. gondii*

T.gondii belongs to the phylum Apicomplexa, class Coccidia and subclass Eucoccidiorida, this classified according to [25] as follows:

Kingdom: Animalia

Sub Kingdom: Protozoa
 Phylum: Apicomplexa
 Class: Coccidia
 Subclass: Eucoccidiorida
 Order: Eimeriorina
 Suborder: Eimeriina
 Family: Sarcocystidae

Genus: *Toxoplasma*
 Species: *T.gondii*

Basic Structure and Life Cycle

There are three infectious stages of *T. gondii*: the tachyzoites (in groups or clones), the bradyzoites (in tissue cysts), and the sporozoites (in oocysts). These stages are linked in a complex life cycle (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Life cycle of *T. gondii*

Tachyzoites

The term “tachyzoite” (tachos = speed in Greek) was coined by Frenkel [21] to describe the stage that rapidly multiplied in any cell of the intermediate host and in nonintestinal epithelial cells of the definitive host. The term “tachyzoite” replaces the previously used term “trophozoite” (trophicos = feeding in Greek). Tachyzoites have also been termed endodyzoites or endozoites. Aggregates of numerous tachyzoites are called clones, terminal colonies, or groups. The tachyzoite is often crescent shaped, approximately 2 by 6 μm (Fig.2) with a pointed anterior (conoidal) end and a rounded end. Ultrastructurally, the tachyzoite

consists of various organelles and inclusion bodies including a pellicle (outer covering), apical rings, polar rings, conoid, rhoptries, micronemes, micropore, mitochondrion, subpellicular microtubules, endoplasmic reticulum, Golgi complex, ribosomes, rough and smooth endoplasmic reticula, micropore, nucleus, dense granules, amylopectin granules (which may be absent), and a multiple-membrane-bound plastid-like organelle which has also been called a Golgi adjunct or apicoplast. The nucleus is usually situated toward the central area of the cell and contains clumps of chromatin and a centrally- located nucleolus [22,23].

Figure 2: Tachyzoites of *T. gondii*. A Dividing Tachyzoite (Arrowheads) and Single Tachyzoites (Arrows). Impression Smear Feline Lung, Stained with Giemsa Stain

The pellicle consists of three membranes, a plasmalemma and two closely applied membranes that form an inner membrane complex which is formed from a patchwork of flattened vesicles [17-19].

The Inner membrane is discontinuous at the anterior tip above the polar rings, at micropores which are situated laterally, and at the posterior pore at the extreme posterior tip of the zoite. Polar ring 1 is an electron-dense thickening of the inner membrane complex at the anterior end of the tachyzoite, which encircles a cylindrical, truncated cone called the conoid, which consists of six to eight microtubular elements wound like a compressed spring. Twenty-two subpellicular microtubules originate from polar ring 2

and run longitudinally almost the entire length of the cell just beneath the inner membrane complex. In addition, two inner microtubules terminate in the conoid. The microtubules are like a rib cage and are arranged in a gentle spiral. Individual microtubules have prominent transverse striations [14].

Between the anterior tip and the nucleus, there are 8 to 10 club-shaped organelles [11] called rhoptries. Rhoptries are excretory structures, each consisting of an anterior narrow neck up to 2.5 μm long that extends into the interior of the conoid, and a saclike, often labyrinthine posterior end (up to 1 μm long). Micronemes are rod-like structures which occur mostly at the anterior end of the parasite (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Schematic Drawings of a Tachyzoite (Left) and a Bradyzoite (Right) of *T. gondii*. The Drawings are Composites of Electron Micrographs

Although tachyzoites can move by gliding, flexing, undulating, and rotating, they have no visible means of locomotion such as cilia, flagella, or pseudopodia. The functions of the conoid, rhoptries, micropores, and micronemes are not fully known but are probably associated with host cell penetration and creation of an intracellular environment suitable for parasite growth and development. The conoid can rotate, tilt, extend, and retract as the parasite probes the host cell plasmalemma immediately before penetration [20].

Rhoptries have a secretory function associated with host cell penetration, secreting their contents through the plasmalemma just above the conoid to the exterior [22].

They contain a proteolytic enzyme [7]. The micropore is a cytosome-like structure formed by the invagination of the outer membrane of the pellicle [9,11,12].

Enter host cells by actively penetrating through the host cell plasmalemma or by phagocytosis [12,14].

After entering the host cell, the tachyzoite becomes ovoid and is surrounded by a parasitophorous vacuole (PV), which appears to be derived from both the parasite and the host cell. Soon after penetration, a tubulovesicular membranous network (TMN) develops

within the PV. Some of the TMN membranes are connected to the parasitophorous vacuolar membrane [12,17-19].

The TMN appears to be derived from the posterior end of the tachyzoite [23]. However, convoluted tubules, structurally similar to the TMN, were observed at the end of tachyzoites by Nichols et al., and we have also observed similar structures in in vivo-cultured tachyzoites [24].

Tachyzoites multiply asexually within the host cell by repeated endodyogeny, a specialized form of reproduction in which two progeny form within the parent parasite (Fig.3) consuming it [25].

In endodyogeny, the Golgi complex divides first, becoming two complexes at the anterior end of the nucleus. Next, the anterior portions of the inner membrane complexes and the subpellicular microtubules of the progeny cells appear as two dome-shaped structures anteriorly. The parasite nucleus becomes horseshoe shaped, and the ends of the nucleus move into the dome-shaped anterior ends of the developing progeny. The inner membrane complex and subpellicular microtubules continue to extend posteriorly and surround one half of the nucleus, which

eventually pinches into two. The progeny continues to grow until they reach the surface of the parent. The inner membrane complex of the parent disappears, and its outer membrane becomes the plasmalemma of the progeny cells. Tachyzoites continue to divide by endodyogeny [21].

In vivo, most groups of tachyzoites are arranged randomly due to asynchronous cycles of endodyogeny. However, rosettes are occasionally formed due to synchronous division. In rapidly dividing tissue culture-adapted strains, *T. gondii* within a vacuole may divide synchronously [22], but this is not the norm. Rarely, tachyzoites of certain strains divide by binary fission [13,14].

The rates of invasion and growth vary depending on the strain of *T. gondii* and the type of host cells [15].

After entry of tachyzoites into a host cell, there is a variable lag period before the parasite divides, and this lag phase is partly parasite dependent [15].

Mouse virulent strains of *T. gondii* grow faster in cell culture than do "avirulent" strains, and some strains of *T. gondii* form more rosettes than others [15].

Although *T. gondii* isolates have been classified genetically into types I, II, and III, there are no appreciable structural differences among different isolates of *T. gondii* [17-19].

Bradyzoites and Tissue Cysts

The term "bradyzoite" (brady = slow in Greek) was also coined by Frenkel [25] to describe the organism multiplying slowly within a tissue cyst. Bradyzoites are also called cystozoites.

Tissue cysts grow and remain intracellular as the bradyzoites divide by endodyogeny.

Tissue cysts vary in size; young tissue cysts may be as small as 5 μm in diameter and contain only two bradyzoites, while older ones may contain hundreds of organisms. Tissue cysts in the brain are often spheroidal and rarely reach a diameter of 70 μm , whereas intramuscular cysts are elongated and may be 100 μm long [22,23].

Although tissue cysts may develop in visceral organs, including the lungs, liver, and kidneys, they are more prevalent in the neural and muscular tissues, including the brain, eyes, and skeletal and cardiac muscles. Intact tissue cysts probably do not cause any harm and can persist for the life of the host without causing a host inflammatory response.

The tissue cyst wall is elastic and thin (<0.5 μm thick), and it encloses hundreds of crescent-shaped bradyzoites, each approximately 7 by 1.5 μm in size.

The tissue cyst develops within the host cell cytoplasm. The cyst wall is argyrophilic [26,27], but results vary depending on the silver impregnation method used. According to Sims et al. [27], the cyst walls stain intensely with Bodian protoargol and Palmgren silver but not with methenamine silver. The lack of staining

with methenamine silver indicates that the cyst wall contains no glycogen or other polysaccharides. The cyst wall is composed of host cell and parasite materials.

It is ultimately lined with granular material, which also fills the space between the bradyzoites. Some bradyzoites degenerate, especially in older tissue cysts. The cyst wall is only faintly periodic Acid-Schiff (PAS) positive [28].

Bradyzoites differ structurally only slightly from tachyzoites. They have a nucleus situated toward the posterior end, whereas the nucleus in tachyzoites is more centrally located. The contents of rhoptries in bradyzoites are usually electron dense, whereas those in tachyzoites are labyrinthine. However, the contents of rhoptries in bradyzoites vary with the age of the tissue cyst. Bradyzoites in younger tissue cysts may have labyrinthine rhoptries, whereas those in older tissue cysts are electron dense. Also, most bradyzoites have one to three rhoptries, which are looped back on themselves (Fig. 3). Bradyzoites contain several amylopectin granules which stain red with PAS reagent; such material is either in discrete particles or absent in tachyzoites (Fig. 3). Bradyzoites are slenderer than are tachyzoites. Bradyzoites are less susceptible to destruction by proteolytic enzymes than are tachyzoites [29], and the prepatent period in cats following feeding of bradyzoites is shorter than that following feeding of tachyzoites [30].

Oocysts

Unsporulated oocysts are subspherical to spherical and are 10 by 12 μm in diameter. Under light microscopy, the oocyst wall consists of two colorless layers. Polar granules are absent, and the sporont almost fills the oocyst. Sporulation occurs outside the cat within 1 to 5 days of excretion depending upon aeration and temperature. Sporulated oocysts are subspherical to ellipsoidal and are 11 by 13 μm in diameter. Each oocyst contains two ellipsoidal sporocysts without Stieda bodies. Sporocysts measure 6 by 8 μm . A sporocyst residuum is present; there is no oocyst residuum. Each sporocyst contains four sporozoites. The ultrastructure of sporulation was described by Ferguson et al. [30].

The cytoplasm of the unsporulated oocyst (zygote) has a large nucleus with amorphous nucleoplasm and a distinct nucleolus. The zygote is limited by a unit membrane with few micropores. The nucleus divides twice, giving rise to four nuclei, which are situated at the periphery of the zygote; at this stage a second limiting membrane is formed. After the cytoplasm divides, two spherical sporoblasts are formed, each with two nuclei [30].

As the sporulation continues, the sporoblasts elongate and sporocysts are formed. The two outer membranes of the sporoblasts become the outer layer of the sporocyst wall, and the plasmalemma of the cytoplasmic mass becomes the inner layer [29].

Ultimately, as the sporocyst develops, four curved plates form the innermost layer of the sporocyst. The plates are joined by four liplike sutures (described below) with a depression on the surface of the sporocyst wall at the junction point. Sporozoite formation begins when two dense plaques (anlagen) appear at both ends of the sporocyst. Each nucleus divides into two and is incorporated into elongating sporozoite anlagen. Thus, four sporozoites are formed in each sporocyst [23].

A prominent residual body is left after sporozoite are formed; the residual body is enclosed in a single-unit membrane [24].

Ultrastructurally, the oocyst wall of sporulated oocysts consists of three layers: an electron-dense outer layer, an electron-lucent middle layer, and a moderately electron-dense inner layer [26].

The middle layer consists of remnants of two membranes that evidently were laid down between the inner and outer layers during oocyst wall formation. Treatment of oocysts with 1.3% sodium hypochlorite (Clorox) removes the outer layer. The oocyst wall contains a single micropyle, which is relatively small and is located randomly in the oocyst wall. The

micropyle is a 350-nm-diameter indentation that consists of three layers that are continuous with the three layers in the oocyst wall. However, the outer layer of the micropyle is thin and moderately electron dense and the inner layer is electron dense, disk shaped, and slightly thicker than the inner layer of the oocyst walls. Although the function of the micropyle is not known, it might represent a permeable site in the oocyst wall that is susceptible to the actions of CO₂ and various enzymes that allow the entry of bile salts and trypsin, which stimulate the excystation of sporozoites from sporocysts. The sporocyst wall consists of two distinct layers with a thin, electron-dense outer layer and thicker, moderately electron-dense inner layer. The inner layer consists of four curved plates [22,27].

At sites of apposition between two plates, there are two opposing liplike thickenings and an interposed strip in the inner layer [26,27].

During excystation in the presence of bile salts and trypsin, the sporocyst ruptures suddenly, evidently at the sites of apposition between plates, releasing the sporozoites. As the plates separate, they curl inward to form conical coils. The sporocyst residuum consists of amylopectin granules and lipid bodies (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Freshly excysted sporozoite still within an oocyst. Am, amylopectin; Co, conoid; Dg, electron-dense granule; Go, Golgi complex; Im, inner membrane complex; Lb, lipid body; Mi, mitochondrion; Mn, microneme; Ow, oocyst wall; PI, plasmalemma; Rh, rhoptry; Sm, subpellicular microtubule; Sw, sporocyst wall

Ultrastructurally, the sporozoite is similar to the tachyzoite, except that there is an abundance of micronemes, rhoptries, and amylopectin granules in the former. Sporozoites are 2 by 6 to 8 μm in size with a subterminal nucleus (Fig. 4 and 5). There are no crystalloid bodies or any refractile bodies in *T. gondii* sporozoites (Fig.4 and 5).

The ultrastructural differences of some of the organelles in tachyzoites, bradyzoites, and sporozoites of the VEG strain of *T. gondii* are compared in Tables 11 and 22; the VEG strain was isolated from the blood of an AIDS patient and is mildly virulent to mice depending on the stage of the parasite inoculated [28,29].

Figure 5: Schematic Drawing of a *T. gondii* Sporozoite

All three zoites have similar numbers of rhoptries but the rhoptries differ in appearance between the zoites. For example, the rhoptries of tachyzoites are uniformly labyrinthine; sporozoites usually contain both labyrinthine and uniformly electron-dense rhoptries; and bradyzoites usually contain uniformly electron-dense rhoptries, some of which are folded back on themselves (Fig. 6).

Tachyzoites have few micronemes, sporozoites have an intermediate number, and bradyzoites have many. Dense granules are more numerous in sporozoites and tachyzoites than in bradyzoites (Fig.5). Amylopectin granules are numerous and relatively large in sporozoites and bradyzoites but are few and small or absent in tachyzoites. Lipid bodies are numerous in sporozoites, rare in tachyzoites, and absent in bradyzoites (Fig.5).

Figure 6: Bradyzoite in the tissue cyst shown in Am, amylopectin granule; Ce, centrioles; Co, conoid; Dg, electron-dense granule; Ga, Golgi adjunct (apicoplast); Go, Golgi complex; Im, inner membrane complex; Mi, mitochondrion; Mn, microneme; Nu nucleus; Pm, plasmalemma; Rh, rhoptry

Structure and Biology Host cells Parasitized and Prevalence

T. gondii tissue cysts occur in many organs and cell types. Most observations have been made with tissue cysts in the brains of mice, but the acid-pepsin digestion procedure and bioassay in cats have shown that tissue

cysts occur in many extraneural organs. Tissue cyst distribution is in part controlled by the host and strain of *T. gondii*. The distribution of tissue cysts in different organs of animals fed the GT-1 strain of *T. gondii* is shown in Table 1. In pigs, dogs, cats, and rodents fed oocysts of the VEG strain of *T. gondii*, more tissue cysts

were found in muscular tissues than in the brain in cats, dogs, and pigs whereas more tissue cysts were found in the brain than in other organs in rats and mice [29-33]. Infections with *T. gondii* in experimental animals appear to be essentially the same as in some naturally infected animals as reviewed by Dubey and Beattie [34]. For example, Jacobs et al. isolated *T. gondii* from 18 diaphragms and 9 brains of 31 seropositive sheep killed at a slaughterhouse in New Zealand [35].

Table 1: Instruments and tools

NO	Instruments and tools	Company	Origin
1	Syringe	Vightof	chain
2	Alcohol	Almos	Emarat
3	Cotton	Alsalama	Iraq
4	Get tube	AR thAIRafidin	Jordn

5	Pipette	Dragon lab	Chain
6	Tourniquet	Vightop	Chain
7	Blue tips	Wafi	Iraq
8	Yellow tips	Wafi	Iraq
9	Centrifuge	Hettich	Germany
10	Maclomi 800	Snibe	Germany

Collection of samples

Data were collected from Al-Rifai Teaching Hospital, Virology Department, from 12/1/2023 to 3/28/2024 from women who suffer from infertility and abortion problems who had a serological examination performed in the laboratory using an ELISA device, and the results were based on the reading of the high aminoglobin Igm titer. Likewise, Igg collected data for 100 samples from the laboratory, after which statistical analysis of the data was conducted.

Figure 7: Maclomi 800 ELISA Device

Women Sample

The total number of blood samples collected from women who had abortion or who suffered from infertility problems was 100, and serological tests

showed that 22 women out of 100 samples were infected with toxoplasmosis, as shown in the table (3-1).

Table 2: Shows Number and Percentage of Toxoplasma gondii that Collected from Women

Number of cases	Positive isolation of parasite species	Percentage %from total number
100	22	22%

Figure 8: The Percentage of Toxoplasma gondii Infection According to Age Groups

In the figure 8 shows the percentage of infection with *Toxoplasma gondii* according to age group It was found that the age group from twenty-nine to thirty-three had the largest infection rate compared to the rest of the ages, followed by the oldest and youngest groups with the same percentage of infection, and the least, infected group were the ages younger than twenty-two and older than thirty –nine these age groups, young and old, have a lower rate of pregnancy due to menopause or the short age of young married women.

In figure (3-2) shows the percentage of age twenty-nine is high was equal 45% and followed by age group from twenty –four to twenty-eight and thirty-four to thirty-

eight in 23% and the least of them are age from nineteen–twenty-three to thirty-nine-forty-three in 5% and 4%.

Figure 9: Incidence Rates for Each Age Group with Toxoplasmosis

Discussion

In the sample of our current study, 100 cases were taken, and it was found that the number of infected people was 22, as positive results were found for the analysis of Toxoplasma bacteria. It was found that the rate of infection with *Toxoplasma gondii* increased within the age group from twenty-nine to thirty- three, which had the highest infection rate compared with many studies

In addition, many to the rest of the ages. This result has been compared with many studies, the reason for these differences is due to the difference in the population and sample of the study in addition to the difference in the categories into which the sample was divided.

This is due to the high rates of Infection with *Toxoplasma gondii* among individuals aged twenty-nine to thirty-three years can be attributed to various factors, including behavioral changes, pregnancy, decreased immune function, and occupational exposure. These residents may engage in activities that increase their exposure to parasites, such as outdoor activities and handling raw meat. Furthermore, pregnancy in this age group increases concern due to the possibility of transmission of infection to the fetus. Enhancing health education, prenatal screening, and workplace safety measures is recommended to reduce infection rates. Further research is warranted to elucidate the underlying causes and interventions designed to mitigate the public health burden posed by toxoplasmosis within this demographic.

While it was found that infection with Toxoplasma bacteria was recorded at the lowest rates for ages within the category [19-23]. These results were compared with the studies mentioned previously, in addition to many studies, and we did not find any consistency in the results. The reason for this is due to the difference in the population and the number of sample members. It may be that the reason for the decrease in the number of infections can be attributed

to many reasons. The reasons can be attributed to behavioral factors such as improving hygiene practices, enhancing awareness

Through education, lower pregnancy rates, stronger immune responses, healthy eating habits, and lack of outdoor activities that expose them to the parasite. Despite the decline in infection rates, preventive measures remain crucial, especially for vulnerable groups, focusing on hygiene, proper food handling and avoiding contaminated environments [18].

Conclusion

1- The current study demonstrated the presence of a *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite infection in laboratory-tested samples.

2- There is a disparity in the infection rate between different age groups

Recommendation

1- Conduct further research and investigation into infection with the *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite at all ages and for different genders.

2- The use of more advanced diagnostic devices for infection with the *Toxoplasma gondii* parasite, such as the polymerase gene reaction device.

3- Study the epidemiological aspect of the spread of the infection in women, the reasons for its spread, and the methods of transmission of the infection.

4- Spreading awareness about the disease, its methods of transmission, and limiting its spread.

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